

Inoculation of Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi for Revegetation of Ex-Mining Land

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Plant Physiology is one of the many existing branches of Biology. Plant Physiology focuses its study on the physiological processes that occur in plants. In plant physiology there are several subjects of study, namely plant metabolism, plant nutrition, plant ecophysiology, mycorrhizal biology, seed physiology and phytohormones. Plant physiology is closely related to ecology and microbiology. Microbiology is a branch of biology that studies micro-sized living things. In mycorrhizal biology, the relationship between microbiology and plant physiology is shown in the association between mycorrhizae and plant roots. Where, by studying the physiological processes of plants, it will be possible to produce a method to improve the ex-mining land using the arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi.

Mycorrhizae undergo a symbiotic relationship with plant roots. This is in accordance with the opinion of Smith and Read (2008) where it is explained that mycorrhizae is a form of symbiotic mutualism between certain fungi and high-level plant roots. This symbiosis occurs when the fungi obtain carbohydrates and other growth elements from the host plant, as well as the plants getting help from the fungi in the process of nutrient absorption. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) are classified into the endomycorrhizal group. It is characterized by the infected roots not enlarging and the hyphae enter individual cortical tissue cells (Yusnaini, 2014). Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi have a very wide distribution and are associated with many types of plants. This is in accordance with Smith & Read (2008) which states that more than 80% of plant species are associated with Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi.

Mining activities have a significant impact on the environment. Mining causes a high content of heavy metals in the soil. Ex-mined soil also has a low pH due to high concentrations of Al and Fe, and low organic matter content (Hasnelly et al., 2006). According to Sujitno (2007), ex-mining land usually experiences a decrease in soil physical and chemical properties. As a result of the displacement of the soil layer above the coal, the topsoil and subsoil are displaced and overturned, causing the parent material to appear on the surface. This results in loss of soil organic matter. Soil that is poor in organic matter will be difficult to support water and fertilizer because organic matter plays an important role as a buffer for the physical and chemical properties of the soil. Organic matter is also a soil colloid which plays an important role in the formation of micro aggregates and colloid absorption complexes. According to Wahyuni et al., (2014), environmental impacts due to the gold mining activities include the decreased of soil productivity, soil compaction, erosion and sedimentation, and also causes soil movement and landslides. Mining waste dumps can pollute rivers and accumulate in low vegetation and can stop oxygen supply to plant roots. This condition causes the land cannot be used as agricultural land and animal life. Land that has been degrade due to mining activities poses many obstacles in the effort to revegetate the land because the fertility level of the land is low (Alifah et al., 2014). For this reason, efforts are

needed so that the land can be productive. Efforts to restore ex-mining land can be carried out through reclamation and revegetation programs of ex-mining land.

Land reclamation efforts include the restoration of ex-mining land where the ultimate goal is the creation of ex-mining land in a safe and stable condition to be overgrown by plants and inhabited by other organisms. The success in remediating ex-mining land is also determined by the addition of organic matter in the soil, because it used as an indicator of soil fertility (Kumalasari et al., 2014) AMF acts as a biological fertilizer, which is the right alternative to improve, improve and maintain soil quality so as to significantly increase yields and crop quality. According to Noor (2012), mycorrhizae play an important role in increasing the absorption of water and nutrients by plants through their symbiosis by increasing the absorption area and removing exudates (organic acids) which can dissolve P elements from an insoluble form. Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) can provide essential nutrients for plants such as phosphorus which plays an important role in energy formation and increasing the speed of plant growth. The symbiosis of AMF with plant roots will provide a wide range of root systems, where the hyphae of AMF will exit the cortex and penetrate the outer skin layer of the plant roots. These AMF hyphae will increase the absorption of nutrients from the soil and transport them to other plant parts. According to Sartini (2004), mycorrhizal inoculated plants were able to increase the absorption of nutrients N, K, Mg, and Zn. In addition, the external hyphae of AMF help increase water absorption which is very useful in the photosynthesis process and increases fertilization efficiency (Murtalaksono, 2014).

Based on the results of research by Rossiana (2003), it was shown that sengon plants inoculated with mycorrhizae were able to reduce the content of Pb, Zn and Cu in the extracted oil sludge waste medium. Then according to Maulidesta (2005), giving AMF can increase the dry weight of *Pueraria javanica* compared to without giving AMF on ex-tin mining land. From the results of Siregar's research (2014), it was shown that giving mycorrhizae was able to increase plant growth, such as plant height, wet and dry weight of plants, wet weight and dry weight of roots compared to plants without mycorrhizal inoculation. According to Siregar (2014), more heavy metal Hg was accumulated by mycorrhizal inoculated plant roots compared to plants without mycorrhizal inoculation. This is because the roots that contain mycorrhizal hyphae play a role in accumulating heavy metals.

Mycorrhizal association with plants will help the plant growth process. When the ex-mining land has been successfully overgrown by plants, it can be interpreted that slowly the land has begun to recover and can gradually return to its original state. Revegetation of ex-mining land can be done by inoculating arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi on plants to be planted on the land. With the presence of mycorrhizae, it will affect the soil structure, such as soil aggregates and soil pore spaces. Through the formation of soil aggregates it will allow better aeration in conditions of low soil water content. With the increasing volume of soil that is used as the water absorption area, the opportunities for plants to absorb nutrients and water are greater than plants without mycorrhizae.

References

- Alifa, N., Noli, Z. A., & Suwirman. (2014). *Respon tanaman Bayur (Pterospermum javanicum Jungh.) terhadap inokulan Fungi Mikoriza Arbuskula (FMA) padalahan bekas Tambang Semen Padang*. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Biodiversitas dan Ekologi Tropika Indonesia. Fakultas Matematika dan Ilmu Pengetahuan Alam. Universitas Andalas.
- Hasnelly, Z., Herwan, Nurhayati, Nuraini & Hasan, R. (2006). *Pemanfaatan Lahan Bekas Tambang Timah melalui Integrasi Tanaman dan Ternak*. Lokakarya Nasional Pengembangan Jejaring Litkaji Sistem Integrasi Tanaman – Ternak.
- Kumalasari P., Noli, Z. A., Febria, F. A. (2013). *Kandungan Logam Berat Merkuri (Hg) Pada Tanah Bekas Tambang Emas di Sijunjung Sumatera Barat*. Unpublish. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Biodiversitas dan Ekologi Tropika Indonesia. Fakultas Matematika dan Ilmu Pengetahuan Alam. Universitas Andalas.
- Maulidesta, N. (2005). *Efek pemberian mikoriza dan pembenah tanah terhadap produksi leguminosa pada media tailing liat dari pasca penambangan timah*. Skripsi. Fakultas Peternakan. IPB. Bogor.
- Murtiaksono, A. (2004). *Pemberian mikoriza dan pupuk kalium terhadap peningkatan produktivitas akar dan komponen hasil hanjeli (Coix lacryma jobi L.) pada lahan kering Jatinangor*. Jurnal Fakultas Pertanian Universitas Padjajaran.
- Noor, A. (2012). *Peranan dan Mekanisme Tanaman yang Bersimbiosis dengan Mikoriza dalam Meningkatkan Serapan Fosfat pada Tanah Masam*. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Inovasi Teknologi Berbasis Ketahanan Pangan Berkelanjutan. Balai Pengkajian Teknologi Pertanian, Kalimantan Selatan.
- Rossiana, N. (2003). *Penurunan Kandungan Logam Berat Dan Pertumbuhan Tanaman Sengon (Paraserianthes falcataria L (Nielsen) Bermikoriza Dalam Medium Limbah Lumpur Minyak Hasil Ekstraksi*. Laboratorium Mikrobiologi dan Biologi Lingkungan Jurusan Biologi. Fakultas Matematika dan Ilmu Pengetahuan Alam. Universitas Padjajaran.
- Sartini. (2004). *Mikoriza Arbuskular dan Kascing: Pengaruh Terhadap Pertumbuhan Tanaman*. JURNAL BIDANG ILMU PERTANIAN 2: 3638.
- Siregar, D. A., Noli, Z. A., & Febria, F. A (2014). *Pengaruh Fungi Mikoriza Arbuskula (FMA) pada tanaman Centrosema pubescens (Benth.) untuk bioremediasi lahan tercemar Merkuri*. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Biodiversitas dan Ekologi Tropika Indonesia. Fakultas Matematika dan Ilmu Pengetahuan Alam. Universitas Andalas.
- Smith, S.E., & D.J. Read. (2008). *Mychorrhiza Symbiosis*. Third edition: Academic Press. Elsevier Ltd. New York, London, Burlington, San Diego.
- Sujitno S. (2007). *Sejarah Timah di Pulau Bangka*. PT.Tambang Timah Tbk. Pangkalpinang.

Wahyuni, F., Noli, Z. A., Febria, F. A.. 2013. *Survey Pendahuluan Kandungan Logam Berat Merkuri (Hg) Pada Tanah Bekas Tambang Emas di Sijunjung Sumatera Barat*. Unpublished. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Biodiversitas dan Ekologi Tropika Indonesia. Fakultas Matematika dan Ilmu Pengetahuan Alam. Universitas Andalas.

Yusnaini S. (2014). *Pengelolaan Hara Fosfor Secara Biologis Kunci Pertanian Berkelanjutan*. Lembaga Penelitian. Universitas Lampung.